

Influence of some Inorganic Additives on Corrosion of Aluminium in Phosphoric Acid

HESHAM MANSOUR

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science at Qena, Qena, Egypt

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The effect of F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and CN^- on the corrosion of Al in 5.0 M H_3PO_4 reveals that fluoride and chloride ions have an acceleration effect while bromide, iodide, nitrate and cyanide ions act as inhibitors. The influence of time and temperature on the corrosion rate has been also studied. Polarisation measurements were carried out galvanostatically vs S.C.E. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

MANY workers¹⁻⁸ studied the corrosion of aluminium and its alloys in phosphoric acid solutions. The effect of organic and inorganic compounds on the corrosion of Al in H_3PO_4 has been also investigated. But little attention has been given to the effect of inorganic compounds on the corrosion of aluminium in phosphoric acid. The present study was therefore undertaken to investigate the effect of fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate and cyanide ions on the corrosion of aluminium in phosphoric acid solutions.

Experimental

The acid and all chemicals (AnalaR) were used without further purification. The composition of the aluminium sheets used for the present work was as follows: Mn, 0.1; Si, 0.1; Fe, 0.1%. The procedures for preparing, testing and cleaning of specimens were carried out according to Champion's technique⁴. Rectangular specimens (5 × 2 cm) were used in weight-loss experiments. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Duplicate specimens were used to check accuracy of the experiments. The loss in weight during dissolution was determined compleximetrically⁵. The experiments were carried out in an air-thermostat (25 ± 0.1°). The percentage inhibition (*I*) was calculated as given by Sanyal and Sanyal⁶. The potentials were measured galvanostatically vs S.C.E. using a precision potentiometer.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed (Table 1) that bromide, iodide, nitrate and cyanide ions decrease the corrosion of aluminium at all the concentrations used. The inhibition efficiency increases with the increase in concentration and attains a region of constancy at concentrations more than 10 mM in case of bromide and iodide ions. Whereas fluoride and chloride ions increase the corrosion of

aluminium in 5.0 M H_3PO_4 at all the concentrations used.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ADDITIVE CONCENTRATION ON WEIGHT-LOSS OF Al IN 5.0 M H_3PO_4 *

Concn. mM	V_{corr} (mg dm ⁻² h ⁻¹)					
	NaF	KOI	NaBr	KI	KNO ₃	KCN
0.0	47	47	47	47	47	47
2.0	51 (-8.5)	57 (-21.2)	46 (2.1)	44 (6.3)	43 (8.5)	39 (17)
4.0	53 (-12.7)	61 (-29.7)	43 (8.5)	40 (14.9)	42 (10.6)	37 (21.2)
5.0	58 (-23.4)	64 (-36.1)	41 (12.7)	38 (19.1)	40 (14.9)	35 (25.5)
6.0	60 (-27.6)	68 (-44.6)	38 (19.1)	34 (27.6)	38 (19.1)	33 (29.7)
8.0	65 (-38.2)	76 (-61.7)	35 (25.5)	30 (36.1)	36 (23.4)	31 (34.0)
10.0	70 (-48.7)	83 (-76.5)	31 (34.0)	24 (48.9)	32 (31.9)	28 (40.4)
15.0	73 (-55.3)	87 (-85.1)	30 (36.1)	25 (46.8)	32 (31.9)	28 (51.0)
20.0	78 (-65.9)	95 (-102.1)	31 (34.0)	24 (48.9)	29 (38.3)	18 (61.7)
30	84 (-78.7)	108 (-129.7)	31 (34.0)	25 (46.8)	27 (42.5)	13 (72.3)

*Values in parenthesis indicate % inhibition.

The acceleration effect of F^- and Cl^- may be due to the formation of HF and HCl in solution which could dissolve the insoluble layer (phosphate formed or oxide film) on the metal surface. The observed high acceleration effect of Cl^- with respect to F^- could be ascribed to intermolecular hydrogen bonds between HF molecules. Another factor, the formation of $AlCl_3$ and AlF_3 in this medium may play a role in the dissolution of aluminium, since $AlCl_3$ is very soluble in such medium while the solubility of AlF_3 is very poor.

The inhibition effect of bromide and iodide ions could be ascribed to their adsorption on the metal surface and their weak effect on the stability of protective surface layer. Therefore, the adsorption of these ions could decrease the corrosion of aluminium in phosphoric acid to some extent. On

the other hand, the observed high inhibition efficiency of I^- with respect to Br^- may be attributed to their ionic radius which may be arranged in the sequence, $I^- > Br^-$. The region of constancy observed in presence of Br^- and I^- at concentrations more than 10 mM could be due to complete coverage of surface by these ions. The inhibitive action of nitrate ions is attributed to the oxidising property of nitrate ions which participate in strengthening the protective oxide film present on the metal surface. The high inhibition efficiency observed in presence of cyanide ions could be attributed to the formation of insoluble salts protecting the metal surface to some extent. The inhibition action of Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and CN^- is confirmed by polarisation studies as can be seen in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1 it is obvious that the addition of 10 mM of additives increases the cathode polarisation of Al in

Fig. 1. Influence of current density on cathode potential of Al in 5.0 M H_3PO_4 in absence and presence of 10 mM additives: (1) KCN, (2) KI, (3) KNO_3 , (4) NaBr, (5) blank, (6) KCl, and (7) NaF.

5.0 M H_3PO_4 , e.g. at the current density 5 mA cm^{-2} , the shift in cathode potential is 360, 255, 175 and 145 mV in presence of CN^- , I^- , Br^- and NO_3^- , respectively. On the other hand, the presence of F^- or Cl^- decreases the cathode potential to a lesser extent. The shift of potential in the -ve direction is a direct consequence of the adsorption of inhibitor molecules on the metal surface. The values of inhibition efficiency evaluated from polarisation measurements are presented in Table 2 for the corrosion of Al in 5.0 M H_3PO_4 in the presence of

TABLE 2—CORROSION CURRENT DENSITY AND % INHIBITION OF AL IN 5.0 M H_3PO_4 CONTAINING 10 mM ADDITIVES BY WEIGHT-LOSS AND POLARISATION METHODS

Compd.	Corrosion C.d. mA cm^{-2}	% Inhibition	
		Polarisation	Weight-loss
Nil	0.14	—	—
NaF	0.195	-39.28	-48.7
KCl	0.24	-71.42	-76.5
NaBr	0.09	35.71	34.0
KI	0.08	42.85	48.9
KNO_3	0.10	28.57	31.9
KCN	0.085	39.28	40.4

10 mM of additives. From Table 2 it is clear that the inhibition efficiencies for the additives are in a good agreement with those estimated by weight-loss measurements.

The effect of time on the corrosion of Al in 5.0 M H_3PO_4 in the absence and presence of 10 mM of additives is given in Table 3. It is obvious that the corrosion rate increases with time in all the cases. The acceleration action of F^- and Cl^- increases with time which could be attributed to the dissolution of protective film on metal surface with the passage of time. On the other hand, in case of Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and CN^- (Table 3), the inhibition efficiency slightly increases with time.

The overall reactions during the acid corrosion in presence of the studied additives could be suggested as follows :

where, $R^- = Br^-, I^-, NO_3^-$ and CN^- ; $AlR^{(3-n)}$ represents a products which may be a salt or a complex which might be stable and retard corrosion. The reactions (3-6) accelerate the corrosion process.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TIME (h) ON WEIGHT-LOSS OF AL IN 5.0 M H_3PO_4 IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF 10 mM OF ADDITIVE*

Compd.	V_{corr} (mg dm^{-2})				
	0.5	1	2	3	4 (h)
Nil	14	47	64	78	90
NaF	20	70	96	120	141
KCl	(-42.8)	(-48.7)	(-50.0)	(-53.8)	(-56.6)
	24	83	112	138	166
NaBr	(-71.4)	(-76.5)	(-75.0)	(-77.0)	(-84.0)
	10	31	42	51	60
KI	(28.5)	(34.0)	(34.3)	(34.6)	(33.3)
	8	24	32	40	48
KNO_3	(42.8)	(48.9)	(50.0)	(48.7)	(52.2)
	10	32	44	50	54
KCN	(28.5)	(31.9)	(31.2)	(35.9)	(40.0)
	9	28	37	45	51
	(35.7)	(40.4)	(42.1)	(42.3)	(43.3)

*Values in parenthesis show % inhibition.

The effect of temperature on the inhibition efficiency has been investigated and the data are recorded in Table 4. From Table 4 it is evident that the inhibition efficiencies of Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and CN^- decrease with the rise in temperature. This behaviour could be due to the decrease of adsorption of anions at higher temperatures. Another factor of significant contribution, the decrease in inhibition may be due to the less dissolved oxygen at higher temperatures.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON WEIGHT-LOSS OF Al IN 5.0 M H₃PO₄ IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF 10 mM ADDITIVES*

Compd.	V _{corr} (mg dm ⁻² h ⁻¹)			
	25°	30°	40°	50° (°C)
Nil	47	74	174	397
NaF	70	112	267	619
	(-48.7)	(-51.0)	(-53.4)	(-56.0)
KCl	83.0	132	313	718
	(-76.5)	(-78.3)	(-79.8)	(-80.8)
NaBr	31	52	130	322
	(34.0)	(29.5)	(25.2)	(18.9)
KI	24	41	111	274
	(48.9)	(44.5)	(36.2)	(31.0)
KNO ₃	32	51	122	286
	(31.9)	(31.0)	(29.8)	(27.9)
KCN	28	46	123	306
	(40.4)	(37.8)	(29.3)	(22.9)

*Values in parenthesis show % inhibition.

The activation energies (*E*) in the absence and presence of 10 mM of additives were evaluated from plots of 1/*T* against log corrosion rates, according to Arrhenius equation. The heat of adsorption (ΔH_a°), free energy of adsorption (ΔG_a°) and entropy of adsorption (ΔS_a°) were evaluated⁷ for additives acted as inhibitors only. The data are recorded in Table 5. The results show that the values of activation energy are lower in presence of inhibitors than that in their absence, while higher values were obtained in presence of accelerators (Cl⁻ and F⁻) with respect to that in H₃PO₄ only. These values confirm the inhibition and acceleration actions of the additives used⁸. On the other hand, the values of heat of adsorption (Table 5) are relatively small which indicates that the adsorption of inhibitors occurs easily and may be of physical type. The free energy values for adsorption are negative which shows strong interaction of inhibitor molecules on according Al surface⁹.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF ADSORPTION OF Al IN 5.0 M H₃PO₄ IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF 10 mM ADDITIVES

Compd.	Temp °C	<i>E</i>		ΔH_a°	ΔG_a°	ΔS_a°
		cal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	cal mol ⁻¹
Nil	—	15.75	—	—	—	—
NaF	—	16.19	—	—	—	—
KCl	—	16.62	—	—	—	—
	25			3.32		21.11
NaBr	30	14.00	2.96	3.25		20.55
	40			3.23		19.80
	50			3.10		18.78
	25			3.68		21.22
KI	30	13.12	2.63	3.64		20.73
	40			3.55		19.77
	50			3.51		19.05
	25			3.26		13.55
KNO ₃	30	13.56	0.77	3.29		13.42
	40			3.37		13.24
	50			3.42		12.97
	25			3.48		22.02
KCN	30	13.34	3.07	3.47		21.63
	40			3.36		20.56
	50			3.25		19.59

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